

THE EFFECT OF 6 FEBRUARY KAHRAMANMARAS EARTHQUAKE ON FORENSIC CASES ADMITTED TO THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT

Keywords

Earthquake,

Emergency Service,

Forensic Case,

Traffic Accident

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ABSTRACT

The earthquake that occurred in Kahramanmaraş is one of the biggest natural disasters that Turkey has faced in recent years. In this study, we aimed to show the effect of earthquake on forensic cases. 4549 forensic cases admitted to the emergency department were compared in terms of age groups, gender, forensic case types, discharge status, months of admission and forensic types before and after the earthquake. While the number of patients admitted to the emergency department increased after the earthquake, the rate of forensic cases decreased (from 6.86% to 3.18%). While the rate of forensic cases decreased after the earthquake, the rates of traffic accidents and occupational accidents increased ($p < 0.001$). In both earthquake periods, the rate of occupational accidents was higher in men ($p < 0.001$). After the earthquake, the rates of in-vehicle traffic accidents, out-of-vehicle traffic accidents and motorbike accidents increased, while the rates of burns, falls from height, and sharps injuries decreased. The rate of forensic cases realised as suicide was higher in women than in men in both periods, while the rate of male suicide increased in the post-earthquake period ($p < 0.05$). The significant increase in traffic accident rates after the earthquake indicates that post-earthquake relief and evacuation activities may increase traffic accidents. Although female suicide rates were high in all periods, the increase in male suicide rates in the post-earthquake period indicates that psychological support activities should be taken into consideration for both genders.

INTRODUCTION

Earthquakes are one of the most destructive natural disasters that directly alter the physical structure of the earth, cause widespread loss of life and property, and shake the social, economic and psychological fabric of society. The sudden and unpredictable nature of earthquakes makes it difficult for individuals, communities and systems to be prepared. In such large-scale disasters, health systems are at the forefront of healing the physical and psychological wounds of society¹. The chaos during and after earthquakes has traumatic effects on individuals and communities. In this process, individuals are more likely to be involved in criminal cases. Economic losses, social insecurity and psychological stress can lead to increased crime rates and suicide attempts². Especially after large-scale earthquakes, a heavy burden is placed on health systems and justice mechanisms. Proper management of forensic cases is critical both to protect the rights of individuals and to maintain social order³.

On February 6, 2023, an earthquake, centered in Kahramanmaraş and affecting many provinces including Hatay, was recorded as one of the biggest natural disasters Turkey has faced in recent years. The impact of the earthquake was not limited to physical damage; it also deeply affected the social order, the psychological state of individuals and the dynamics of forensic cases. In the post-disaster period, changes were observed in the type and frequency of forensic cases encountered especially in emergency services. These changes are an important source of data to understand how social dynamics and individual behaviors are shaped in the post-disaster period.

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Any event that causes a person's health to deteriorate, injury or death as a result of intent, negligence, recklessness or carelessness of oneself or others is defined as a forensic case^{4,5}.

The aim of this study is to analyze the forensic cases admitted to emergency services in Hatay following the February 6 earthquake centered in Kahramanmaraş. This analysis aims to assess the impact of large-scale natural disasters on forensic events by examining the types, demographic characteristics and presentation patterns of forensic cases. The study is expected to contribute to the development of health and justice systems for similar disaster situations in the future. We do not have enough data to show the effect of earthquake on forensic cases. In this study, we aimed to show the effect of earthquake on forensic cases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Department of Emergency Medicine. In our study, the 6 months before and the same period after the earthquake that occurred on February 6, 2023, which was centered in Kahramanmaraş and affected Hatay province to a great extent, were taken. In the period after the earthquake, in the period immediately after the earthquake, Hatay Mustafa Kemal University emergency service was also affected by the earthquake and its use had to be suspended, so services had to be provided in the field hospital in the 6-month period immediately after the earthquake.

Therefore, the second 6-month period after the earthquake and the period 1 year before the earthquake were selected to coincide with the same period. The sample of our study consisted of 4549 forensic cases admitted to the emergency department on the specified dates. These forensic cases were compared in terms of age groups, gender, types of forensic cases, discharge status, and months of admission according to the earthquake period. In order to examine forensic cases in detail according to their types, 2773 forensic cases were included after excluding occupational accidents and some forensic cases from 4549 patients. Adult (over 18 years of age) and pediatric (under 18 years of age) forensic cases were included in the study.

Forensic case types excluded; work accidents, simple home accidents, simple child falls, simple school accidents, elderly falls, suspicious situations or traumas that are unlikely to be forensic. The excluded forensic cases are outside the types of forensic cases that we want to examine in the research and were excluded because they contain highly suspicious and unlikely to be forensic cases.

The relationship between two independent variables at the categorical measurement level was analyzed with Pearson and Exact Chi-square tests. Number and percentage values were given for categorical variables as descriptive statistics. SPSS Windows version 24.0 package program was used for statistical analysis and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 4549 patients, of which 2538 (6.86%) were forensic cases before the earthquake and 2011 (3.18%) were forensic cases after the earthquake, were admitted to the emergency department. The total number of patients admitted to the emergency department before and after the earthquake was 100250. The rate of forensic cases admitted to the emergency department before the earthquake was higher ($p=0.05$).

The rate of forensic cases under 18 years of age before the earthquake was higher than after the earthquake, while the rate of forensic cases over 18 years of age before the earthquake was lower than after the earthquake ($p=0.001$). The rate of male forensic cases was higher after the earthquake than before the earthquake. The rate of female forensic cases before the earthquake was higher than after the earthquake ($p = 0.011$). While the rate of judicial cases decreased after the earthquake, the rate of traffic accidents and occupational accidents increased ($p < 0.001$). After the earthquake, the rates of discharge with cure and hospitalization in the ward increased, while the rates of voluntary discharge, death and intensive hospitalization decreased ($p < 0.001$). Table 1 shows the comparison of forensic cases in the pre- and post-earthquake period according to age group, gender, forensic status and discharge status.

		Earthquake Period				
		Pre-Earthquake		Post-Earthquake		p
		n	%*	n	%*	
Age group	<18	764	30,1	516	25,7	0,001
	>18	1774	69,9	1495	74,3	
Gender	Male	1716	67,6	1430	71,1	0,011
	Female	822	32,4	581	28,9	
Forensic Cases	Forensic Situation	1795	70,7	951	47,3	<0,001
	Traffic Accident	476	18,8	794	39,5	
	Work Accident	267	10,5	266	13,2	
Discharge	Discharged with Recovery	1943	76,6	1695	84,3	<0,001
	Voluntary discharge	23	0,9	6	0,3	
	Death	25	1,0	9	0,4	
	Service hospitalization	23	0,9	276	13,7	
	Intensive care hospitalization	524	20,6	25	1,2	

* Percentage of column

Table 1. Comparison of the distribution of forensic cases before and after the earthquake

Figure 1. Evaluation of forensic cases according to months of admission

In the pre-earthquake period, the rate of forensic cases was higher in August and September. In the post-earthquake period, the rate of forensic cases was higher in October, November and December ($p < 0.001$) (Figure 1.).

Also in both periods, the rate of male occupational accidents was higher than that of females ($p < 0.001$).

2773 forensic cases admitted to the emergency department before and after the earthquake were compared. After the earthquake, the rates of In-vehicle traffic accidents, Out-of-vehicle traffic accidents, Motorcycle accidents increased, while the rates of Burns, Fall from height, and Sharps injuries decreased ($p < 0.001$). (Table 2.)

Type of forensic cases	Earthquake Period						
	Pre-Earthquake (n=1362)		Post-Earthquake (n=1411)		Total (n=2773)		
	n	%*	n	%	n	%*	p
In-vehicle traffic accident	247	18,1	317	22,5	564	20,3	0,005
Out of-vehicle traffic accident	51	3,7	77	5,5	128	4,6	0,032
Motorcycle accident	255	18,7	435	30,8	690	24,9	<0,001
Stabbing	39	2,9	38	2,7	77	2,8	0,785
Assault	190	14,0	180	12,8	370	13,3	0,356
Firearm Injury	43	3,2	52	3,7	95	3,4	0,445
Burn	68	5,0	25	1,8	93	3,4	<0,001
Environmental emergencies	16	1,2	24	1,7	40	1,4	0,245
Falling from a height	148	10,9	88	6,2	236	8,5	<0,001
Foreign body ingestion	27	2,0	18	1,3	45	1,6	0,141
Intoxication	140	10,3	120	8,5	260	9,4	0,109
Injury by sharp piercing instrument	138	10,1	37	2,6	175	6,3	<0,001

*Percentage of column

Table 2: Comparison of forensic cases by earthquake period

A total of 260 intoxication cases were evaluated before and after the earthquake. Detergents, corrosive substances and drugs-alcohol were found to be higher before the earthquake (Table 3.).

	Earthquake Period						
	Pre-Earthquake (n=140)		Post-Earthquake (n=120)		Total (n=260)		
	n	%*	n	%*	n	%*	p
Intoxication							
Medical Drugs	33	23,6	51	42,5	84	32,3	0,067
Detergent corrosive caustic agent	54	38,6	28	23,3	82	31,5	0,002
Carbon monoxide	9	6,4	19	15,8	28	10,8	0,071
Mushroom	11	7,9	6	5,0	17	6,5	0,197
Pesticide-Organophosphate	12	8,6	8	6,7	20	7,7	0,329
Drug substance-Alcohol	21	15	8	6,7	29	11,2	0,012

*Percentage of column

Table 3: Distribution of intoxication cases by type

The comparison of suicide cases by earthquake period and gender. After the earthquake, male suicide rate increased while female suicide rate decreased. In both periods, the female suicide rate was higher than the male suicide rate ($p<0.001$) (Table 4.)

	Pre-Earthquake (n=41)					Post-Earthquake (n=47)				
	Male		Female		p	Male		Female		p
	n	%*	n	%*		n	%*	n	%*	
Suicide	10	24,4	31	75,6	<0,001	17	36,2	30	63,8	<0,001

*Line percentage

Table 4: Comparison of suicide cases by earthquake period and gender

DISCUSSION

Earthquakes have caused not only physical destruction and loss of life, but also significant changes in terms of forensic cases. In this study, the analysis of forensic cases before and after the earthquake provides important findings in terms of understanding the effects of disasters on the health system.

Although the total number of patients increased after the earthquake, the percentage of forensic cases decreased ($p < 0.001$). In the study by Almedia et al. analyzing the patients admitted to the emergency department after the Nepal earthquake in 2015, an increase in the number of patients admitted to the emergency department after the earthquake was observed in parallel with our study⁸. Again, when we look at the literature, in the study titled the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the emergency department conducted by Ertuğrul et al. at Cerrahpaşa University, a decrease in forensic case rates was observed after the pandemic⁹. These findings are compatible with our study.

When the characteristics of the admitted forensic cases were compared according to the earthquake period, the rate of male forensic cases increased in the post-earthquake period in our study (71.1%), while the rate of female forensic cases decreased (28.9%). ($p = 0.011$) When we look at the literature, in the study titled Evaluation of forensic cases admitted to the emergency department conducted by Zeren et al. at Mustafa Kemal University in 2011, the rate of male forensic cases was found to be higher than the rate of female forensic cases, similar to the pre-earthquake period in our study¹⁰. Again, in the study titled Evaluation of forensic cases during the Covid 19 pandemic period conducted by Çıkrıkçı et al.¹⁰. In the study titled Evaluation of forensic cases during the Covid 19 pandemic period by Çıkrıkçı et al. the rate of male forensic cases was found to be higher than the rate of female forensic cases both before and after the pandemic and it was shown that the rate of male forensic cases increased¹¹. In a study titled Gender Specific Issues in Traumatic Injury and Resuscitation conducted in the United States of America, it was shown that forensic cases were higher in men¹².

When forensic cases are evaluated in terms of age groups, the majority of forensic cases (71.9%) consisted of individuals over the age of 18. While the rate of individuals under 18 years of age was 30.1% before the earthquake, this rate

decreased to 25.7% after the earthquake. In both periods, the rate of forensic cases over the age of 18 was higher than the rate of forensic cases under the age of 18 ($p = 0.001$). When we look at the literature, in the study titled Evaluation of forensic cases admitted to the emergency department conducted by Zeren, Karakuş et al. at Mustafa Kemal University in 2011, the adult age group was higher, which is in parallel with the pre-earthquake period in our study¹⁰. Again, in the study titled the effect of Covid 19 pandemic on forensic cases conducted by Doğan et al. In the study titled the effect of Covid 19 pandemic on forensic cases, the rate of forensic cases over the age of 18 was found to be high in both periods and the rate of forensic cases over the age of 18 decreased after the pandemic¹³.

The proportion of patients discharged with a cure after the earthquake increased from 76.6% to 84.3%, while intensive care hospitalizations decreased from 20.6% to 1.2%. The proportion of patients who died decreased (from 1.0% to 0.4%). Doocy et al. showed that mortality rates increased after the Haiti earthquake, while Shimada et al. showed that intensive care hospitalizations increased after the Great Japanese earthquake. Similarly, in the study conducted by Aydın et al. after the Kahramanmaraş earthquake, it was shown that intensive care hospitalizations increased¹⁴⁻¹⁶. While it was expected that intensive care hospitalizations and mortality rates would increase after the earthquake when we look at the literature, the opposite results were found in our study.

When the distribution of forensic cases according to the months of admission was analyzed, it was observed that forensic case rates were high in August and September in the pre-earthquake period (19.5% and 18.7%), and increased in December and January after the earthquake (18.6% and 17.8%). It is noteworthy that forensic case rates increased in the winter months, especially in the post-earthquake period ($p < 0.001$). When we look at the literature, the study conducted at Cerrahpaşa University, where the effect of pandemic on forensic cases was examined, shows similarities with the increase in forensic cases in winter months, as in our study⁹. While most of the forensic cases showed a similar distribution in the pre-earthquake period, post-earthquake forensic cases were concentrated immediately after the disaster. In 2011, in the study titled Evaluation of forensic cases admitted to the emergency department of Mustafa

Kemal University, the distribution of forensic cases according to months before the earthquake was similar to our study, with a higher number in the summer months, while forensic cases in the post-earthquake period were concentrated in the winter months¹⁰.

When the types of forensic cases were evaluated after the earthquake, it was shown that while the rate of traffic accidents and occupational accidents increased after the earthquake, the rate of forensic cases decreased ($p < 0.001$). A remarkable change was observed in the distribution of forensic event types. Helton et al. reported that the rate of traffic accidents increased after the earthquake¹⁷. These findings support the findings of our study. However, in contrast to our study, in the study conducted by Doğan et al. during the pandemic period, the rate of traffic accidents and judicial cases decreased while the rate of motor accidents increased. It was thought that the decrease in the number of traffic accidents in periods when traffic density decreased during the pandemic was due to the curfew¹³.

The rate of occupational accidents increased in men after the earthquake. In the study conducted by Alp et al. evaluating occupational accidents and Karakurt et al. The rate of male occupational accidents was found to be higher than the rate of female occupational accidents in the studies conducted by Alp et al.^{18,19}. Again, in the study conducted by Hekimoğlu et al. In the study conducted by Van Earthquake Investigating occupational accidents after the Van earthquake, it was shown that the rate of occupational accidents increased by 63% after the earthquake and most of the occupational accidents occurred in men. This increase was attributed to the increase in construction activities after the earthquake²⁰.

When we make a detailed comparison of the types of forensic cases according to the earthquake period, we observe significant changes in the rates of cases such as motor vehicle accidents (MVA), vehicular traffic accidents (VTA) and non-vehicular traffic accidents (NVTA) in the pre- and post-earthquake periods. After the earthquake, the rates of AITC, MTC and ADTAC increased. In the study conducted by Kandış et al. in which forensic traumas in the geriatric age group were evaluated, it was shown that the forensic case with the highest rate was MTC²¹. In our study, the rate of MTC was found to be the highest among the forensic case rates in both earthquake periods. The ICC rate, which was 18.7% before the

earthquake, increased to 30.8% after the earthquake ($p < 0.001$). In a study conducted by Casey et al. In a study conducted by²², it was shown that motor accidents increased after the earthquake²². The reason for this was the increased stress after the earthquake. Similar to this study, it was observed that the rate of motor accidents increased after the Kumamoto earthquake in Japan in 2016, supporting our study²³.

Rates of burns, falls from height and sharps injuries decreased after the earthquake. In the study conducted by Dursun et al. In the study conducted by Dursun et al. when post-earthquake burn cases were analyzed, burn cases increased in the first 3 months after the earthquake²⁴. In the study conducted by Albonoz et al. Albonoz et al. found no difference between pre- and post-earthquake burn cases²⁵. The fact that there are different findings about burn cases in the literature is thought to be related to the fact that the studies were conducted in different time periods after the earthquake. Kuno et al. Kuno et al. examined the cases of falls after the Great Japan earthquake and showed that the cases of falls increased after the earthquake. He suggests that the reason for this is due to psychological distress after the earthquake. Unlike our study, this study found an increase in fall cases, but does not provide sufficient data on falls from height²⁶. Doğan et al. In the study by Doğan et al. examining the effect of Covid 19 pandemic on forensic cases, contrary to our study, cases of falling from height increased¹³. Gielen et al. When we look at the study in which they examined domestic accidents during the pandemic period, it was shown that the cases of falls increased due to the increase in domestic accidents during the pandemic period²⁷. It is thought that the reason for the decrease in cases of falling from height after the earthquake may be the decrease in domestic life due to changes in shelter facilities.

The rate of sharps injuries decreased from 10.1% in the pre-earthquake period to 2.6% after the earthquake ($p < 0.001$). Çıkırıççı et al. In the study titled "Evaluation of forensic cases during the Covid 19 pandemic period" conducted by Çıkırıççı et al. it was observed that the rate of sharps injuries increased after the pandemic, contrary to our study¹¹. Çavuş et al. According to the study in which they examined the effect of the Covid pandemic on hand surgery, it was shown that there was an increase in sharps injuries due to the increase in the time spent at home during the Covid 19 pandemic²⁸. It was thought that the decrease in domestic life due to changes in shelter facilities after the earthquake may be the reason for the

decrease in sharps injuries in our study. No significant relationship was found between other judicial events and the earthquake period.

No significant correlation was found between intoxication cases and the earthquake period, but when we examined the distribution of intoxication cases according to their types, detergent, corrosive and caustic substance intoxications decreased from 38.6% to 23.3% after the earthquake ($p=0.002$). Intoxication due to drug and alcohol use also decreased from 15.0% to 6.7% ($p=0.012$). No significant relationship was found between other types of intoxication and the earthquake period. When we look at the literature, in contrast to our study, these studies conducted in the USA and Italy have shown that the rates of alcohol and substance use increase especially in young people after major disasters such as earthquakes or hurricanes. However, these studies do not mention the effect of increasing rates of alcohol and substance use in young people on emergency room visits^{29,30}.

Deniz, et al. In a study conducted by Deniz et al. in which poisoning cases admitted to the emergency department were evaluated, it was observed that most of the drug intoxication cases were performed for suicide³¹. In another study conducted by Sönmez et al. In another study conducted by Sönmez et al. in which poisoning cases were evaluated, it was shown that most of the poisoning cases were realized for suicide³². In our study, it was observed that most of the poisoning cases were realized for suicide. When the effect of gender and earthquake period on suicide cases was analyzed, the rate of male suicide cases increased after the earthquake (from 24.4% to 36.2%), while the rate of female suicide cases decreased (from 75.6% to 63.8%). However, in both periods, the rate of female forensic cases was higher than that of males. ($p<0.001$) In the study by Kato et al. comparing suicide cases after the Great Japan earthquake, suicide cases increased in parallel with our study³³.

Again, when the suicide rates after the Great Japanese earthquake by Kuroda et al. were examined, it was shown that the suicide rate of men increased immediately after the disaster, while the suicide rate of women increased later than men.⁽³⁴⁾ While these findings are in parallel with our study, in the study by Orui et al. on the change in suicide rates after the Great Japanese earthquake, male suicide rates decreased after the earthquake, while female suicide rates increased in the

disaster-affected regions. However, in this study, job opportunities were offered to those in the earthquake zone and bankruptcies were prevented. It was found that providing job opportunities to those in the earthquake zone and reducing bankruptcy cases may have a protective effect on male suicide rates in control areas³⁵.

CONCLUSION

The 2023 earthquakes centered in Kahramanmaraş attracted attention not only with their physical destruction and loss of life, but also with their impact on forensic cases. While the total number of patients increased after the earthquake, the proportion of forensic cases decreased. This was associated with increased workload in emergency departments and intensive admissions of non-trauma patients. The increase in the proportion of male forensic cases and the decrease in the proportion of female cases showed gender-based differences. The predominance of adult cases revealed that the rate of children being evaluated as forensic cases may decrease.

The increase in traffic accidents is attributed to the intensification of logistic mobility after the earthquake, while the increase in occupational accidents points to reconstruction activities. The decrease in the rates of domestic accidents such as burns, falls from height and sharp-piercing instrument injuries was thought to be due to the restriction of domestic living space. Suicide rates in women were found to be high in all periods, but male suicide rates increased after the earthquake, which suggests that post-disaster psychological support should be considered for both genders. Although there are studies in the literature on cases admitted to the emergency department in the acute period after the earthquake, studies evaluating the effects of the earthquake after the acute period are insufficient. Our study reveals the long-term effects of the earthquake on forensic cases.

Descriptions

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